
New York's Climate Smart Communities Program

A Study of Climate Policy Capacity in NY Towns and Villages

Stakeholder Report, April 2025

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Executive Summary

New York's Climate Smart Communities (CSC) program is administered by the state's Department of Environmental Conservation (DEC) and provides a framework for counties, cities, towns, and villages to receive certification as *climate smart* after completing a series of actions and accomplishments related to climate change mitigation and adaptation, including activities related to planning, preparedness, and community building. We sampled twenty CSC-participating towns and villages and conducted interviews with community leaders to learn about their experiences as well as the promises and challenges related to program participation. This report provides an overview of our findings.

● ***Who did we talk to in the Climate Smart Communities program?***

We engaged with individuals actively involved in CSC program planning within their respective communities. Despite their limited resources, small, rural municipalities cover the largest land area in New York State and must have the tools and support needed to build climate resilience policies and programs. We focused on these non-urban communities and sampled twenty (20) communities that are CSC-certified and represent a range of community sizes and contexts. Our conversations included a diverse range of participants: elected officials such as town Supervisors and members of town or village Boards, members of formally established task forces or commissions (e.g., with 501(c) status) dedicated to CSC initiatives and broader environmental efforts³, as well as community volunteers who, while unofficially appointed, have key roles in advancing or leading CSC projects. Some individuals held multiple roles, such as current or retired municipal staff who serve as volunteers for neighboring communities.

Most participants described their community residents as supportive of the climate planning efforts, though some broad but not organized climate skepticism and NIMBYism appeared in a few interviews. For example, there was overwhelming support for a community choice aggregation energy plan in one community, but the community voted down a proposed solar farm given its specific location. Community climate skeptic sentiments were never mentioned as an opposing organized effort, though opposition to climate programs in some specific town or village leadership positions was discussed as a factor limiting efforts.

³ Sometimes these official task forces predated community participation in the CSC program.

● ***Why*** were these communities motivated to initiate participation in the CSC program?

In many cases, the impetus for community CSC program participation was an interested community member or group who was passionate about environmental stewardship. Sometimes, the impetus came from elected officials or staff who heard about the program and were motivated by environmental sentiments, the potential for financial benefits (i.e., grant money), a desire for public recognition, community pride, or a combination of these factors. Many spoke of the desire for their community to do their part for climate change and be good stewards, but perceived financial benefits, through CSC grant eligibility⁴, were a reason for program participation cited in nearly all interviews. For communities with more resources and the ambition to achieve higher levels of certification, competition and the desire to be among the state's CSC leaders were described as other forms of motivation.

Most individuals did not cite specific weather-related natural hazards or resulting community disasters as an impetus for joining the CSC program, but some participants did mention recent heavy flooding events or heavy snowfall events as at least somewhat influential in steering program participation. More than one interviewee mentioned climate adaptation planning, i.e., planning designed to adapt to climate change, as a driving force, as opposed to climate mitigation planning, i.e., planning designed to reduce climate emissions, as a reason communities joined the CSC program. Some individuals reported their community's participation began when they were contacted about the CSC program by representatives from NYSERDA, the DEC, and regional planning and development boards. Another mentioned the community leadership first heard about it through being included in the (e)mail distribution lists of state-level organizations such as The New York Conference of Mayors.

● ***How*** did communities participate in the CSC program in terms of resources that were essential?

Given our chosen focus, many interviewees discussed an implicit bias toward urban communities in the way the program is structured, and this shows up in at least three ways. First, specific items on the CSC program list, such as Complete Streets or public transit-related policies, simply do not pertain to the work of small and rural communities. Second, given the size of the community, in-house staff do not always have the technical knowledge and skills to complete certification actions such as greenhouse gas inventories or resilience assessments. Third, given that financial resources are tight in a

⁴ All local governments are eligible for the CSC and Zero Emission Vehicle (ZEV) grants managed by the DEC. It is not a requirement that the municipality be a registered or certified CSC to apply for these funds, but registered and certified CSCs earn extra points in the scoring systems for some NYS grants.

small rural community, there is less opportunity to find and spend resources on paid outside consultants and other sources of external support, such as CEC regional coordinators.

With that said, many communities engaged with the CSC program using a combination of in-house staff and volunteers. Some communities used internal financial resources and outside grant money to hire consultants to complete certain CSC certification actions; this was especially true for the completion of complex reports such as climate action plans or vulnerability assessments.

● ***What impacts came as a result of community CSC program participation?***

One of the most common outcomes of CSC program participation we observed was grant money secured by the community as a result of actions taken. This grant money was usually used for infrastructure upgrades to buildings and hiring staff to help support CSC-related programs. Another outcome was the passage and enactment of resolutions and policies within communities, typically related to CSC certification actions (sometimes called action items). A third outcome was public outreach events for CSC participation, and these events, too, were often tied to CSC certification actions, such as community education events regarding home heat pumps and rebates. In terms of specific infrastructure projects tied to CSC objectives, a common outcome for communities was the installation of public electric vehicle (EV) charging stations. However, these projects can lead to challenges related to grid modernization.

Introduction

Climate change presents profound and far-reaching impacts that challenge communities globally, and New York State is no exception. The state faces numerous climate-related threats, including rising temperatures, increased frequency and intensity of extreme weather events, sea level rise, and shifting precipitation patterns. These changes significantly affect ecosystems, infrastructure, agriculture, water resources, and human health (Stevens and Lamie 2024).

Human health, for example, is directly impacted by climate change. Increased temperatures can lead to heat-related illnesses and exacerbate chronic conditions such as cardiovascular and respiratory diseases. In the summer of 2023, New York experienced significant air quality issues due to smoke from Canadian wildfires. The northeastern United States saw hazardous levels of particulate matter, causing public health advisories and highlighting the interconnected nature of climate impacts. Poor air quality from these wildfires posed serious health risks, particularly for vulnerable populations such as children, the elderly, and those with preexisting health conditions. Most of all, this impacted individuals required to work outside, such as farm workers in rural areas.

While 2023 was a particularly bad year, New York's agricultural community is particularly vulnerable to climate change. Rising temperatures and shifting precipitation patterns have disrupted growing seasons, reduced crop yields, and increased the prevalence of pests and diseases. Farmers face more frequent and severe weather events, such as floods and droughts, which can devastate crops and reduce soil fertility. These challenges threaten the viability of agriculture, a vital sector for the state's economy and food security. Understanding and mitigating these impacts is critical for ensuring the resilience and sustainability of New York's diverse communities, including rural agricultural communities (Aller et al. 2024).

New York State has proactively addressed climate change through innovative programs designed to support local municipalities in becoming more resilient and sustainable.

● *What is Climate Planning?*

Climate planning is a process of developing strategies for reducing, or mitigating, a community's greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and preparing for, or adapting to, the impacts of climate change. Climate planning varies from examples of visionary, broad aspirational goal statements, to concrete implementation of specific policy and program detail. Mitigation program efforts might include the promotion of renewable energy

development and adaptation program efforts might include flood prevention. A normative goal for most communities is to engage and involve the public in climate planning, to ensure the specific policies and programs are contextually appropriate for the community's geography and specific to the population and relevant stakeholders. Related to climate mitigation and adaptation planning is resilience planning, or planning related to reinforcing and supporting the ability of communities to recover from events, including climate-related events like storm flooding, heatwaves, and wildfires⁵.

● *The Climate Smart Communities Program*

The [Climate Smart Communities \(CSC\) program](#), established in 2009, encourages municipalities to take action on climate change by providing a comprehensive framework for assessing vulnerabilities, reducing greenhouse gas emissions, and building adaptive capacities to prepare for climate change. The program is an interagency initiative led by the New York State Department of Environmental Conservation (DEC) and supported by various state agencies. It offers a structured pathway for municipalities to achieve certification and recognition for their climate actions.

The CSC program consists of multiple key components within its framework. The [CSC Grant Program](#) is a funding initiative that supports municipalities in carrying out projects aimed at reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and enhancing climate resilience. It also funds specific planning and assessment efforts that contribute to a broader strategy for achieving CSC certification. Additionally, the [Zero-Emission Vehicle \(ZEV\) Program](#) supports municipalities in adopting clean transportation solutions by providing rebates for purchasing or leasing eligible zero-emission vehicles, including all-electric vehicles, plug-in hybrid electric vehicles, and hydrogen fuel cell vehicles. The CSC program also includes [CSC Coordinators](#), who offer free technical support to municipalities across ten different regions in New York State. The CSC regional coordinators assist local municipalities in advancing climate action by promoting greenhouse gas reduction and climate adaptation through outreach, planning, education, and capacity-building initiatives.

The CSC Certification program, launched in 2014, recognizes and celebrates municipalities that reduce their greenhouse gas emissions and adapt to climate change impacts. The program provides a robust toolkit of actions that municipalities can undertake, categorized into 10 elements that comprise the CSC pledge. The pledge elements are: 1) build a climate-smart community, 2) inventory emissions, set goals, and plan for climate action, 3) decrease energy use, 4) shift to clean, renewable energy,

⁵ For an excellent primer on climate planning, see Boswell, Greve, and Seale (2019).

5) use climate-smart materials management, 6) implement climate-smart land use, 7) enhance community resilience to climate change, 8) support a green innovation economy, 9) inform and inspire the public, and 10) engage in an evolving process of climate action. In addition to the 10 pledge elements, there are two additional categories: 11) innovation, which accounts for innovative projects distinct from existing CSC certification actions and novel approaches to certification actions that are not included in the current CSC guidelines and 12) performance, which accounts for reducing GHGs from government facilities and vehicles, and minimize waste generated by government activities. Municipalities earn points for completing actions under each category, which are then used to achieve certification levels ranging from bronze to silver, and eventually to gold⁶. As a note, the program encourages community public participation in many of these certification actions.

Since its inception, the CSC program has made significant strides in engaging local governments across New York State. As of 2024, over 420 municipalities had adopted the CSC pledge, and 150 had been certified at the bronze level or higher. The program's impacts are evident in the diverse projects and initiatives participating communities undertake. These projects range from installing electric vehicle charging stations, upgrading to energy-efficient street lighting, developing comprehensive climate action plans, and conducting community-wide greenhouse gas inventories. The CSC program has thus provided a valuable framework for municipalities to systematically address climate change, leveraging state resources and support to advance local sustainability goals.

● *Other New York Climate Planning Resources*

In addition to the CSC program, New York Communities can also take advantage of the Clean Energy Communities (CEC) program, which promotes clean energy adoption and energy efficiency improvements. Launched in 2016 by the New York State Energy Research and Development Authority (NYSERDA), the CEC program offers financial rewards and recognition to communities for completing high-impact actions. The program complements the CSC program by emphasizing actions that reduce costs, energy consumption, and greenhouse gas emissions through clean energy solutions.

● *Our Research Context*

Despite these supportive frameworks, small and rural municipalities often face substantial challenges when advancing climate action. Limited financial resources, understaffed local governments, and a lack of technical expertise can hinder these

⁶ <https://climatesmart.ny.gov/actions-certification/actions/> (Accessed February 4, 2025)

communities' ability to participate fully in state programs and pursue their climate goals. Some municipalities may struggle to prioritize climate action amidst competing needs and may lack the technical capacity to navigate the complex requirements of New York's climate action planning programs.

Our previous work, detailed in the paper "[Community-based climate action planning as an act of advocacy: a case study of liberal arts education in a rural community](#)," explored the role of higher education institutions in supporting local climate strategies in small, rural municipalities. In that study, we described the formation and activities of the Hamilton Climate Preparedness Working Group (HCPWG), a coalition of elected officials, community members, university staff, faculty, and students focused on climate change planning and advocacy in Hamilton, New York. The success of HCPWG in achieving Climate Smart Community certification for the Town and Village of Hamilton highlighted the potential of university-community partnerships in advancing local climate resilience and sustainability (Pattison, Henke, and Pumilio 2021).

In this context, colleges and universities can be pivotal in supporting local climate action efforts. These institutions possess a wealth of knowledge, technical expertise, and human resources that can be mobilized to assist municipalities in overcoming the barriers they face. Through partnerships and collaborative projects, higher education institutions can provide critical support in areas such as data collection and analysis, public engagement, and the development and implementation of climate action plans.

Building on this foundational work, our current research expands the scope to include a broader range of municipalities across New York State. During the summer of 2023, we conducted 21 semi-structured interviews with representatives of 20 distinct CSC-certified communities and 2 CSC regional coordinators employed by regional planning and developing boards, e.g., Central New York Regional Planning and Development Board. These interviews provided valuable insights into the unique challenges and opportunities faced by midsize and small communities in non-urban counties in their climate action efforts. The interviews also highlighted the diverse ways external technical and organizational support, such as the critical role that regional planning boards, Cornell Cooperative Extension offices, and colleges and universities can play in supporting these municipalities, from technical assistance and policy development to public education and community engagement. This kind of support is referred to as *policy capacity* in the scientific and professional literature.

In the following sections, we will detail our methodology and present the key insights from our interviews with leaders of small, rural communities engaged in climate action planning. These insights highlight the efforts and challenges these communities face as they work to enhance their climate action and sustainability goals. Our goal is to provide

valuable, research-based information that can inform modifications to state programs while supporting municipal leaders and technical/organizational agencies in their collaborative efforts to meet local climate goals. We hope this work will serve as a resource for state agencies, practitioners, and not-for-profit organizations dedicated to fostering effective climate action programs at the municipal level.

In conclusion, addressing the multifaceted challenges of climate change requires concerted efforts from all sectors of society. Despite their limited resources, small, rural municipalities cover the largest land area in New York State. They are on the front lines of climate impacts and must have the tools and support needed to build resilience. State programs must be designed in a way to support small rural communities. Similarly, technical support agencies and organizations such as regional planning boards, cooperative extension offices, and colleges and universities, with their capacity for data collection, research, innovation, and community engagement, are wonderfully positioned to aid these municipalities in navigating the complexities of climate action planning and implementation. By leveraging the strengths of these institutions, we can create more resilient and sustainable communities across New York State.

Methods

In our 2021 study, we examined the Climate Smart Communities (CSC) program to explore the specifics of how local governments of different sizes, ranging across a rural to urban context, and having various levels of affluence, might vary in how the communities can access resources in climate planning work. An example of variation in how a community could access resources would be a community's completion of a greenhouse gas (GHG) inventory as part of the CSC program and whether a staff member, with perhaps limited experience, or a paid professional consulting firm completed the GHG inventory. We specifically focused on the role of, or potential for, higher education institutions as a resource in climate planning. This focus reflected on our experiences working with the Town and Village of Hamilton, New York, in the CSC program dating back to 2016. That study made some generalizations about different CSC participating communities based on population size, population density, relative urbanity-rurality of the area, median income, and percentage of families designated as living in poverty. These data points were drawn from the 2018 American Community Survey and the 2010 US Census, as opposed to direct experience. We wanted to build on the previous study by interviewing key informants in CSC-participating communities to see if our findings were confirmed through direct interviews.

We began our research with a small number of exploratory interviews with state and regional leadership for the Climate Smart Communities and Clean Energy Communities programs to refine our research questions, interview questions, and research plan before moving on to a larger sample of communities. Then, using the CSC website, 2020 [American Community Survey](#) census data, and [Policy Map](#) data, we built a database of all the communities that held certification as a Climate Smart Community as of 2023. This database included 16 counties, 31 villages, 58 towns, and 18 cities.

We then developed a stratified sample that includes communities from a range of characteristics such as population size, population density, type (i.e., village, city, town, and county), and population affluence as measured by median household income. We hypothesized that community affluence could shape a municipality's ability to complete climate policy actions. Given the goals of our research project, we excluded large urban communities like New York City and Buffalo and focused on midsize and small villages and towns in rural or semi-rural counties. In addition, and given our interest in the role of higher education institutions in the CSC planning process, we aimed for about half of our sample to be communities with evidence of working with higher education institutions in their CSC-published documents. Further, we chose our sample with an attempt at covering the state. We will note here that we tried to offer a range of

communities in terms of median household income by comparing the average median income of villages and towns and determining quartile groups that satisfied our needs.

In the summer of 2023, we began contacting the individuals listed in the respective communities' reporting documents provided on the CSC program website. In some cases, we were encouraged to contact alternative or additional people. In the end, we conducted 21 semi-structured interviews with representatives of 20 distinct CSC communities and 2 CSC regional coordinators employed by the state and regional planning organizations. The sample group included elected officials such as town Supervisors and village Mayors, members of town or village Boards, local government staff, and volunteers part of formally established task forces or commissions (e.g., with 501(c) status) dedicated to CSC initiatives and broader environmental efforts and sustainability planning⁷, as well as community volunteers who, while unofficially appointed, have taken on key roles in advancing or leading CSC projects. Some individuals were crossovers of these categories, such as elected or staff officials in a neighboring community but volunteering efforts in their own different home community or long-experienced but retired government officials now volunteering. When presenting our results, we maintain anonymity in our interview participants and the communities they represent.

Our interview guide included questions across numerous CSC-related topics and community planning processes, covering the following themes, presented with some examples of questions:

- Who? *"Tell us about your professional background and the position you hold in your community."*
- Why? *"What were the main motivations for your community initiating the CSC program?"*
- How? *"What resources were essential to your community in seeking/gaining certification?"*
- What? *"How has the CSC program impacted your community?"*

Our complete interview guide is provided in the appendix of this report. The interviews were recorded and transcribed using [Otter.ai](#) software. Next, we used [MAXQDA](#) software to identify emergent themes within and across the interview findings.

⁷ In some communities, these official task forces predated participation in the CSC program.

Results

We group our results into three main sections: 1) an assessment of the CSC and CEC program structures and community experiences working with these frameworks, 2) an assessment of how and to what extent the programs have supported participating communities in building climate preparedness and overall policy capacity, and 3) an assessment of the outcomes of community CSC participation that illustrates both promising and challenging elements of communities' experiences with climate planning.

Results Section 1: Program Structure and the Role of the CSC and CEC Frameworks

One fundamental aspect of the Climate Smart Communities or Clean Energy Communities programs that many of our interviewees discussed was, despite any challenges or frustrations they might have working with the program(s) or online portal(s), they all reported that having a specific framework, and the website portals for the programs, to organize municipal climate action planning is better than not having a framework. Virtually all of our interview participants responded "Yes" when we asked if they would recommend the CSC program to local communities just getting started.

I can't tell you how many times I was on that website, especially when you have to submit everything, and you'll look at it and see what you're missing. And...looking at the website was my go-to resource, you know, and template for what I had to accomplish.

This encourages, I mean, I think it provides a structure...you know, a blueprint and a structure and a format by which to look and identify, you know, discrete actions that you can take. So in that sense, I think it's been incredibly, you know, incredibly helpful.

Another often repeated aspect of the CSC and CEC programs' structure was the way the website and portal system made progress into a competitive game against other communities. In this way, the two programs' structure provides an internal motivation, nudging communities towards further action and policy promulgation.

And you know, like having the point system. It's kind of like we...are competing with other communities. Right now, we're on the... leaderboard for clean energy communities. So that's kind of fun.

Regarding sources of frustration with the programs, many of our interview participants brought up the expiration of points. Even when interview participants acknowledged the logic of expiring points inducing continuous improvement, there were specific critiques of all points expiring.

I don't think it's fair that those points expire that you got for your bronze...why do we have to go through that whole process again, for something that we already did? I really disliked that the points expire.

You know, we got a couple of points for retrofitting all of our streetlights, but you can only do that once. So why would they not count the next time around?

Many communities used the CSC regional coordinators and regional planning organization staff to help review their CSC and CEC program documents and make sense of their application material. However, although regional coordinators were reported as being helpful to communities, the turnover in regional coordinator staff limited the effectiveness of this source of support.

You know what else you can tell people that I didn't know either is that you can have your... Regional Council person review your application before you submit it.

Something that has been difficult for both programs is having coordinators that don't really stay around that long...And so you know that we've had, you know, a lot of gaps. You know, we have several months where we don't have a coordinator. So we kinda worked like relying on somebody from another region...that's been a little challenging.

Interview participants who participated in both the CSC and CEC programs were asked about the differences between the programs; there was general agreement that the CEC program was simpler. The CEC program is, in fact, a shorter list of actions than the CSC certification actions. It was perceived to be easier to read and to offer a tighter link between actions and rewards, either through points or money. In other words, the incentives in the CEC program were clearer and easier to obtain.

That program [the CEC program]...it's a simpler program, and that there's not as many actions and ways to to get points...and there is an overlap between the two. There's more money tied around the Clean Energy one right now. So there's definitely an incentive for communities to complete those actions because...there's grant money there.

One of the motivations for doing a lot of the CSC stuff was actually the CEC program. Because most of the grants we've gotten are actually CEC grants. Being CSC bronze was one point we got toward some of the CEC, but yeah, the CSC program has had a lot less direct benefit.

Some interview participants offered general critiques of the programs, but the frustration usually came down to actions counting for points in one but not the other program.

However, others noted that points for certification in one program, for instance, can count towards points in the other program.

Results Section 2: Community Resources and Policy Capacity

Our research was informed by an interest in the CSC program's potential to develop and support the policy capacity of New York communities. Policy capacity is a concept used to describe the ability (or lack thereof) of organizations to develop initiatives and follow through on goals in political units of all kinds. Kekez et al. (2018: 245) describe policy capacity as "bundles of skills and resources necessary to perform policy functions" and outline the needed staff, organization, and contextual resources required to complete political tasks above and beyond the basic requirements of any municipal government such as adopting an annual budget or meeting staff payroll. For example, developing a municipal policy on green purchasing, vehicle fleet procurement and management, or energy standards are each initiatives that could gain a community points via the CSC Certification program, but does a given municipality know how to get started on one of these efforts? Developing policy requires skills and knowledge among those completing the work, resources and political will among the organization and community, and a broader administrative and political context that supports the goals of the municipality (Kekez et al. 2018: 246). While not all of these factors are necessary conditions for organizations to develop and employ new policies, we hypothesize that increased policy capacity will lead to more effective climate change planning outcomes among the communities in our study.

We group policy capacity into two broad categories: internal and external capacity. Internal capacity includes human capital (e.g., staff skillsets and knowledge), political capital (e.g., legislative experience or community support), and economic capital that a municipality can draw on from within its own operations, such as staff, budget, and volunteers that can support policy projects and goals. In addition, internal capacity includes the political support of municipal government, especially elected members of a town or village board. External capacity also includes human, political, and economic capital, but these resources come from outside the boundaries of the municipal staff and budget. In our study, we looked especially for the presence of technical support from higher education institutions, regional planning groups, and not-for-profit organizations dedicated to climate change planning and environmental protection. In addition, external capacity can come from paid consultants (effectively, hired policy capacity), and budget support can come from grants received from regional, state, or federal sources.

The line between an internal and external source of capacity can often be somewhat blurred. For example, consider the case of a university professor or staff member who serves as a volunteer on the climate task force for a municipality and also contributes data and reports to that community's climate efforts via class projects and research. Each of this report's authors has contributed to our community's climate planning efforts in these ways that might be termed both internal and external contributions to policy capacity. In our data collection for each community in the sample, we sought to clarify the roles and backgrounds of each participant via our interviews with municipal representatives as well as information from application data publicly available on the CSC website. While this data does not always point to a clear line between internal and external sources of capacity, we are able to draw some conclusions about the communities in our sample.

● *Internal Capacity*

We categorized internal capacity through multiple dimensions, including the level of support from the municipal government (as perceived by our interview participants), budget support for climate change work from the municipality, the role and expertise of the municipal lead for that community's CSC certification efforts, and the membership of the CSC task force (a task force is required of all municipalities pursuing CSC certification). Because each of the communities in our sample are certified CSC municipalities, this means that they—by definition—likely already had some policy capacity, and so our sample has a baseline level of capacity that may be required in order for any community to attain certification. Of the 20 municipalities in our sample, 12 interview participants described a town or village board that actively supported efforts toward CSC certification; another 3 described passive support. Only one participant described the challenge of working against an actively hostile municipal leadership. Three communities, however, noted instability in board support, as turnover in elected leaders could swing the board either for or against climate change planning between relatively brief election cycles.

We've worked with probably three different boards over the period...because the composition changes every few years.

Yeah, I'm concerned. We have an election coming up...it's the same issue with all things in the government that some terms are fairly short and you know, you can't really get much done in just a few years. And yeah, we don't have a staff person working on it...like some other larger communities do. So I don't know what will happen with my grant if I don't get re-elected in the fall, and there's a grant to follow up on that next year. Who's going to do that?...I don't know.

Communities in our sample vary widely in the availability of budget resources to support climate change efforts. While many interview participants emphasized the need to complete actions and work toward certification with little or no demands on town or village budgets, specific examples shared by participants revealed different understandings of what “little or no” impact means in practice. In one community, a request for a few hundred dollars to support community outreach related to CSC certification was rejected by a town board of supervisors. In another case, a representative from one of the wealthiest communities in our sample described the limited budgetary resources available to them but also mentioned a \$5000 allocation for that municipality’s climate task force to use toward certification. This does not mean that this interview participant was disingenuous in their description of community resources but rather demonstrates the variability in financial capacity between certified municipalities.

In addition, communities also vary in the backgrounds, skills, and experiences brought by participants in their CSC task forces. We categorized the human capital available to municipalities according to whether participants were paid municipal staff, elected officials, or volunteers, and the relative expertise brought to CSC efforts by these participants. We judged relevant expertise to include prior experience with climate change planning, sustainability or environmental engineering background, or training in planning. Only one community’s task force and CSC effort was entirely comprised of non-expert volunteers. This is not necessarily a negative aspect of that community’s CSC work, and the interview participant we spoke with emphasized the pride and hard work of a volunteer task force. At the same time, this group was starting from a place of much reduced policy capacity compared with other municipalities where volunteers in some cases brought specific technical expertise and worked alongside elected board members, municipal staff, and non-expert volunteers to gain CSC certification. Eight of our 20 communities had task forces with each of these types of participants; only two communities lacked an elected official on their task force. The participation of expert volunteers is diverse and hard to predict, but wealthier communities with denser populations of professionals in and near these municipalities seemed to be more likely to draw on expert volunteers for task force membership and input on specific climate actions.

Overall, despite some variability in the composition of internal task forces, most certified communities in our sample had a strong mix of participants who could bring knowledge, experience, and energy to their work. This finding is related to questions we asked each interview participant about their “starting point” for seeking CSC certification. Several communities already had policies or other actions in progress or completed before pursuing certification and were able to build upon those efforts when beginning the formal process of CSC work. While some participants described these activities as “low

hanging fruit” that were among the easier actions to complete and thereby gain points toward certification, 19 of 20 communities had at least some items that they could build upon when starting the process. The only interview participant who described starting from scratch represented the community with an all-volunteer task force.

● *External Capacity*

Some sources of external capacity—especially work with higher education institutions and regional planning and development boards—were cited by nearly every community in our sample. Only 2 of 20 municipalities seemed not to have at least some support from higher education. The details of this support were more varied and ranged from university faculty or staff who served on the community’s task force to one-time class projects that helped a community complete a climate assessment or develop a strategy for community outreach. Cornell University Cooperative Extension was cited as a frequent source of support, especially in towns and villages located closer to Cornell’s campus, but the statewide presence of Cooperative Extension meant that extension staff were frequently available for support. This finding is perhaps not surprising, given that Cooperative Extension, in particular, has been awarded grants from the DEC and NYSERDA to provide technical assistance to communities seeking CSC certification. Both the CSC and CEC program websites provide contact information that leads interested communities directly to regional sources of technical assistance, explaining in part the prevalence of this source of external capacity among our interview group⁸. Four municipalities also noted the participation of students from local school districts, and one community’s task force included student representatives from their local middle and high schools.

A final source of external policy capacity is paid consultants, typically brought in by municipalities to help complete more complex projects such as climate action plans or vulnerability assessments. These documents and plans can be completed by municipal staff and CSC task force members when those groups have the internal capacity to complete the research, analysis, and planning to complete a project of this type; however, not all communities have the resources to complete this on their own and may lack the time or resources to develop this expertise. This is where consultants specializing in climate change planning may be employed to provide assistance and, in some cases, complete most or all of the steps to develop one of these resources for a community.

⁸ <https://climatesmart.ny.gov/support/csc-coordinators/>

<https://www.nyserderda.ny.gov/All-Programs/Clean-Energy-Communities/Find-a-Participating-Contractor>
(Accessed February 4, 2025)

Consultants are sometimes available for limited or no cost to a community, such as regional coordinators funded by the DEC or NYSERDA to provide this support. As noted in the prior section, many of the communities in our sample cited regional planning and developing boards as a significant resource, and several interview participants praised these groups for their support in gaining CSC certification. This interview participant noted the critical support of one regional coordinator who helped their community complete a Climate Action Plan:

Yeah, and Michael Boccuzzi [from Central New York Regional Planning and Development Board] helped us update our Climate Action Plan. He's been a great help...I don't think we would have done this on our own.

When considering a paid consultant, municipalities have to weigh the viability of paying for the service from their own budget or seeking external sources of funding, such as a grant from New York State. The DEC administers the CSC Grant program on an annual basis and in the most recent round of funding, awarded \$16 million to local governments proposing climate change-related projects (NYSDEC 2024). Grants are an important source of funding for many communities, but they present two key challenges that some communities struggle to meet. First, proposing and managing grants is a complex job that requires its own set of technical expertise. Experienced grant writers are prized by communities and can be an incredibly valuable resource, but one that might require resources to attract and retain, presenting a kind of “chicken and egg” dilemma, especially for communities with fewer resources.

We don't have a grant writer. We've been trying to find a grant writer. If you know anyone please [we] really need a grant writer...The really, really successful grant writers are over capacity right now.

Second, many state grants, including the CSC Grant program, require communities to provide matching funds or in-kind resources such as staff time, typically 50% of the requested amount of the grant. So a municipality seeking \$100,000 to complete a climate action plan could receive \$50,000 from a grant and would be required to provide the other half from their own economic and/or human capital. Many interview participants expressed frustration at the challenge of meeting this 50% match.

So we have a tiny budget, our budget is less than \$6 million a year and even a \$50,000 match for a \$50,000 grant to do a \$100,000 project is the kind of thing that we actually can't put into our budget without raising everyone's taxes on a year to year basis. So we ended up finding out that a lot of those grants were actually not really very available to us for that simple reason, and also because they require an actual match you can't match with other state funding.

Other communities with more discretionary funding in their budgets, or with the potential to share costs with other municipalities, reported fewer barriers to accessing grants with

matching requirements, and in some cases (see the second quotation below) used those funds to complete important work toward their CSC certification efforts.

And I know that the CSC [Grant] program has a 50-50% match...I don't think that would be a barrier for us...I think as long as we know how things are done...we can make an adjustment as to our budget and whatnot.

So we went...after the Climate Smart Communities grant and we were awarded \$25,000 on a matching grant, a 50/50 grant to complete a climate action plan...So because we did a joint study, the town and the village each only paid \$12,500. So we split the match and we got a great product for a good deal. And we were one of the first examples in the state for use of the grant to develop something that got them certified.

In summary, policy capacity impacts the ability of communities to propose and complete climate change actions, and the relative levels of capacity in New York's non-urban towns and villages varies considerably, providing a potential inequity and set of barriers for all state communities to participate in climate change planning and preparedness. This point is further magnified when we consider that all of the communities in our sample *were already certified* as Climate Smart Communities. We do not have data on those communities that have taken initial steps toward CSC certification or never considered getting started; more research would be required to assess the impact on relative policy capacity for all state municipalities.

For those communities with the resources and the initiative to pursue certification and complete CSC actions, this work provides them with the opportunity to develop new skills and ultimately increase policy capacity. This interview participant described the ways that their community's climate action planning process provided a set of new insights and opportunities, with positive influences on broader municipal operations and planning:

A lot of us learned a lot of a lot of things from the Climate Action Plan...So I think it's helping us make more comprehensive decisions in relation to climate change...There's many things that we do at the government level where in years past you would make a decision or think about, think about it, and there wouldn't be this ancillary thought of, well, what about climate change, right? So now when we're out there doing something like replacing a pipe, we're thinking about are we just replacing the same size or are we going to upsize this thing to accommodate the 100 year storm? That's just a general example of how it's taught us to think holistically. And when we work on our update to our comprehensive plan, we'll have a whole section this time on sustainability and climate change adaptation.

Results Section 3: Outcomes of Community CSC Participation

As discussed above, more than half of our interview participants applied for and received grants of some kind as part of the CSC participation. Often, these were used for infrastructure upgrades. Another common use of grant money is to hire and pay for a consultant to increase policy capacity for CSC efforts. In other cases, grants were used to hire part-time staff. We note here that a tradeoff exists between using external policy capacity, e.g., hiring a consultant, and growing internal capacity, e.g., providing staff training for new skills.

We got a \$50,000 grant to do some work at our community center. So we got another \$5,000 that we're going to put towards some heat pumps...the money has obviously been great, and it's been put to good use, and it's it saves taxpayer, you know, saved us from using it out of our budget.

Now we've created this monster right where we have all these projects going, and it's too much for me and my clerk treasurer. So...our last consolidated funding application...we did apply for a Climate Smart Communities grant, and we received funding to hire a person. So we are now going to hire a climate smart coordinator, sustainability coordinator for our community. That's going to be taking care of all of these initiatives sitting on our task force.

A second common outcome of CSC participation was the town or village passing resolutions, such as commitments to moving towards green energy or adopting new policies, such as complete streets policies. Often, these were described as “low hanging fruit” for initial points in the program. And a third outcome was sponsored events designed to raise awareness and educate the community's public on CSC-related matters. These events varied in scale and scope and included community-hosted repair cafes, LED lightbulb (provided by NYSERDA) handouts, electric vehicle events, Earth Day events, and an increased social media presence. These events were described as having hard-to-measure but noticeable benefits, such as nudging community members towards making household sustainability inventories and updates.

With some of those certification steps...everyone's learned to compost... the uptake of compost in our community was probably like, 5%. And now it's, like, 50%, probably. So, you know, that's been a big thing.

Installing electric vehicle (EV) chargers is another CSC-related outcome that many communities have either begun or completed. Multiple interviewees told us stories of how these specific projects can surface the challenges of implementing green technologies on top of older infrastructures in terms of electric grid readiness for new charging demands.

We did get a [zero emission vehicle] grant. We put a charging station into our new park that we put along the creek. It's not networked yet, and...we haven't put in the [direct current fast charging] station because we have to bid out like the whole bidding process and try to figure out the networking strategy and planning for the future has been challenging, for sure.

A related point is that some interview participants discussed the seemingly insurmountable challenges in initiating an electrification of some parts of the government fleet in their communities. Specifically, garbage trucks, fire trucks, and police vehicles were brought up multiple times as impossible to replace with EVs from either the financial or practical sense, e.g., cold weather plowing, for small communities.

Another technology advanced during CSC efforts was the increased visibility of home heat pumps and commensurate rebates available. At least two interview participants discussed community events centered around home heat pumps.

They had a couple of vendors come in, gave a presentation on heat pumps and try to get more community members to enroll in that program.

A final sustainable infrastructure project often resulting from CSC efforts is LED street light retrofits. At least one interview participant mentioned the community was likely to have done the retrofit in any case due to falling prices and technological innovations. Though now that the improvement is worth points in the programs, it was all the more worth it.

We note here that the infrastructural outcomes of CSC participation are, to some extent, a function of the respective community context. For instance, smaller communities that provide fewer services to their citizens will, by nature, have fewer infrastructure systems to upgrade. These communities, much like rural communities, simply do not manage the structures and systems covered by many CSC certification actions and are thus not eligible to receive the corresponding points.

But when I look at the remaining elements, a number of them seem to apply to cities or to more densely populated communities. Because they're raising bicycle pads, making a walkable community, making a bike lane, pedestrian traffic safer, just things we can't do.

We don't have any of those kinds of things to work on and make it improve. We don't have wastewater facilities, we don't have any of those things.

A final outcome of CSC participation we would like to highlight is the more intangible benefit of community learning. Community learning, or policy learning, results from the organizational/institutional self-reflection associated with deliberating each possible CSC certification action in various staff and/or elected official meetings. While many of these actions might be small in scale and have small impacts, each deliberation, and

the respective impacts have a way of accumulating and gradually altering the existing beliefs of staff, elected officials, and citizens in the community.

We've learned things from those actions and the program of how you can improve your town and make it more sustainable and reduce your greenhouse gas emissions.

Conclusion

As of early 2025, more than 150 counties, cities, towns, and villages in New York are certified as Climate Smart Communities, representing 6,251 approved certification actions since 2014 and likely thousands of participants in climate change planning across the state⁹. These numbers alone testify to the success and impact of the program. Our research confirms this success in many cases while also pointing to challenges and barriers that shape the participation of New York State municipalities.

We chose to focus on small, non-urban communities because, while these communities often lack the comprehensive planning resources or policy capacity available to larger, more urban communities, these communities offer the potential for significant overlap between community engagement and climate planning. Community members often know each other from multiple overlapping networks, formal and informal, and there is great potential for the resulting bridges and bonds between community members to pave the way for climate policy appropriate to the respective community context. In this way, programs like the CSC and CEC programs, which nudge the promulgation of local policies, climate and energy policies in this case, can realize their most significant gains in smaller communities in non-urban settings that are often left out of climate planning debates and frameworks.

Nearly every participant in our interviews cited the constraints of limited time and staff capacity, especially when weighing climate change planning against a broad range of other required and desired projects facing any municipality. Those communities that did pursue and attain certification needed to prioritize this goal and marshal internal and external sources of capacity to achieve certification. The CSC program framework provided these municipalities with a structure for getting started with climate change planning and a flexible set of actions to pursue. Many communities required significant sources of external capacity to complete “big ticket” projects such as climate action plans, and support from external sources of capacity such as higher education institutions, regional planning and developing boards, and grant funding were critical to complete these actions. For those municipalities that did achieve certification, the CSC program allowed them to organize their efforts, complete actions, and potentially develop new capacities and community dedication toward climate change planning.

⁹ <https://climatesmart.ny.gov/actions-certification/participating-communities/> (Accessed January 30, 2025)

Our research leaves many questions unanswered, and some avenues for future work might include the following sources of data and key conceptual questions:

- What quantitative indicators of the costs and benefits of CSC participation might be measured for specific communities and NY State more broadly?
- How will the CSC program be integrated with NY State's Climate Act?
- What is the appropriate balance of community effort and growth versus external sources of climate change planning support?
- Can communities sustain their climate change planning efforts if sources of external capacity are reduced or eliminated?
- How can NY State communities with the fewest resources be supported so that they might participate in climate change planning and preparedness?

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Appendix 1: Interview Guide

Who

1. Please tell us about your professional background and the position you hold in your community.
2. What's your main responsibility/work during the certification process?

Why

3. How did your community get to know about the Climate Smart Communities program?
4. What were the main motivations for your community initiating the CSC program?
 - Risks from climate change? Incentives (e.g., grants)? Public Recognition?
 - Has your community dealt with any climate-related and/or officially designated FEMA disasters? Did this disaster impact your community's motivation to participate?
 - Did the impetus come from staff? Elected leaders? Or the public?
 - Is there consensus in your community about climate change? Do people in the community know about and support CSC certification?

How

5. Can you talk about the certification process and the people involved?
 - How did you make the decision to register? (board meeting? Any objections? Key people?)
 - Was the process more reliant on internal resources, e.g., staff within the local government?
 - Or more reliant on external resources, such as a consultant, NGO, or outside agency?
 - How long did it take your community to complete the certification?
6. What resources were essential to your community in seeking/gaining certification?

[e.g. private consultant, NGO consultant, university students or faculty, county or regional or state staff or offices]

 - How did you make decisions about using internal or external resources? Can you give an example?
 - Was there a particular person or group who spearheaded the certification process?
 - What was the total cost of any outside resources?
 - Was budget an essential concern for the community? What was the source of your community's budget for CSC certification?

- From the county/state level, did you receive any instructions/ help that you think is really essential for the community to get certified?
7. Did your community have any specific advantages or disadvantages in seeking certification? What were some of the main obstacles?
 8. Who is a part of your community CSC task force? Whose voices in the community are most represented? Whose voices are left out?

What

9. How has the CSC program impacted your community?
 - Policy outputs/outcomes? What are some changes in your community from the certification process? Do you think they are big changes or small changes to the community?
 - Has CSC certification made your community more aware of climate change?
 - Did the government staff who worked on the certification gain skills/knowledge about climate action planning throughout the process?
 - Getting grants/funds for climate change related projects after certification
10. Do you plan to seek re-certification when your CSC certification is up for renewal?
 - Do you have any concerns about re-certification?
11. Overall, do you think it is worth it for a community to get CSC certification?
12. Does your community participate in the Clean Energy Communities program? Do you see any synergies (or tensions) between the CSC and CEC programs?
13. Are you aware of NY's Climate Leadership & Community Protection Act? From your perspective, has your participation in the CSC program helped your community be ready for The Climate Act?
 - Are you concerned at all about aspects of The Climate Act or implications for your community?

Miscellaneous [just a few questions that we haven't already covered]

14. How would you describe your community in terms of affluence, diversity, etc?
15. Do you think your views on the CSC program participation are representative of your community?
16. Do you have any suggestions for revisions/improvements to the CSC program(s)?
17. Is there anyone else in your community who was involved with the CSC certification that you recommend we talk to? (get contact info).
18. Is there anything you want to add that we haven't covered?

Thank you so much for your time!